

ROAD LIGHTING AND ROAD USER ALERTNESS AT NIGHTTIME: TESTING THE NULL FINDINGS OF GIBBONS AND BHAGAVATHULA

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Abstract

While lighting is expected to have some impact on alertness, previous research in the context of walking or driving in the evening did not reveal a significant effect. Those studies used lighting conditions similar to those considered acceptable for road lighting application. The null finding was tested in the current work by conducting an experiment which also included a lighting condition that would otherwise be considered extreme for road lighting. It was confirmed that alertness was affected for a lighting of CCT 5800 K delivering 83 lx photopic illuminance at the eye.

1 Introduction

This research concerns road lighting for pedestrians. According to CIE 115:2010 (CIE, 2010) the three main purposes of road lighting are: (1) to allow all road users, including operators of motor vehicles, motor cycles, pedal cycles, and animal drawn vehicles to proceed safely; (2) to allow pedestrians to see hazards, orientate themselves, recognize other pedestrians, and give them a sense of security, and; (3) to improve the day-time and night-time appearance of the environment. These purposes relate to aspects of visual performance and visual perception. In recent years, attention has been devoted also to non-visual impacts of lighting such as alertness, also known as vigilance, arousal or sustained attention (Oken et al., 2006).

Alertness describes the activation state of the cerebral cortex and affects the ability to process information: a decrement in alertness means a decline in the performance of tasks requiring attention over an extended period (Mackworth, 1964). Alertness is an important issue for travel because impaired alertness is associated with an increased risk of pedestrian tripping or falling (Woollacott et al., 2002) and increased risk of involvement in a road traffic collision (Bioulac et al., 2017).

Lighting conditions which better stimulate the intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs) gives the potential for improving alertness (Vetter et al., 2022) as the ipRGCs feed into human responses including alertness (Legates et al., 2014). Such lighting conditions are enhanced levels of light in the short wavelength region, as can be modelled using equivalent daylight illuminance (EDI) in melanopic lux (CIE, 2018).

Previous studies (Phipps-Nelson et al., 2009; Plitnick et al., 2010) have shown lighting of enhanced short-wavelength content increases alertness, as investigated through a range of measures. In those studies, however, the procedure was for a relatively dim light level to be followed by exposure to brighter conditions. In the evening, a typical pattern of light exposure is the reverse case, with exposure to relatively bright lighting (in the office or home) followed by exposure to relatively dim road lighting.

Two studies by Gibbons and Bhagavathula used a situation that better resembled the typical evening exposure to road lighting (Bhagavathula et al., 2021; Gibbons et al., 2022).

In Bhagavathula et al. (2021) participants were asked to drive for two hours (01:00 to 03:00) on a closed loop road after a two-hour adaptation period (23:00 to 01:00) under normal home-indoor lighting levels (photopic illuminance 200 lx, melanopic EDI 87 lx, at the eye level of the seated participant). The test track was lit with five lighting conditions, including those typical of

road lighting (CCT of 2100 K and 4000 K and luminances of 0,7 cd·m⁻², 1,0 cd·m⁻² and 1,5 cd·m⁻²) giving melanopic EDI in the range of about 0,3 lx to about 0,8 lx.

In their experiment targeting pedestrian application (Gibbons et al., 2022) the participants were seated on chairs on a closed road for four hours (22:00 to 02:00) after a two-hour adaptation period (20:00 to 22:00) to lighting of the same condition as also used for adaptation in Bhagavathula et al. (2021). This study used six lighting conditions during the test phase, including a luminance of 1,0 cd·m⁻² and CCTs ranging from 2100 K to 5000 K, giving melanopic EDI in the range of about 1,5 lx to 5,7 lx.

In neither study did the results suggest an effect of lighting on alertness, as measured using melatonin levels from saliva samples, self-report of sleepiness, and response to a visual reaction time test. One explanation for this is that the conditions used, chosen to resemble typical outdoor lighting practise, did not provide a melanopic EDI sufficient to evoke a change in alertness.

Alshdaifat et al. (2023) conducted an experiment to test the null finding of Gibbons and Bhagavathula by extending the upper level of melanopic EDI to 10,7 lx. This upper limit was chosen because 10 melanopic lux is the maximum recommended for unavoidable activities for the (at least) three hours before bedtime to avoid melatonin suppression which would affect sleep quality (Brown et al., 2022) – this choice is therefore the maximum that might be used in application. This was a laboratory study, conducted over three hours in the evening (21:00 to 00:00), with two hours of adaptation to lighting resembling a domestic interior (25 photopic lx, 10,7 melanopic lx vertical at eye level, 2700 K) followed by exposure to one of four light conditions defined by melanopic EDI and CCT: < 0,5 lx, 2700 K; 3,4 lx, 2700 K; 10,4 lx, 5800 K; and 10,7 lx, 2700 K. Each test session involved two participants. During the adaptation phase, both were seated. During the test phase one of the participants remained seated and the other walked upon a treadmill to simulate the cognitive demand of maintaining balance while walking. The dependent variables were reaction to an acoustic detection task, melatonin levels derived from saliva samples, self-reported sleepiness, and skin temperature. As with the studies by Gibbons and Bhagavathula, the results did not suggest a significant difference between these lighting conditions on either of the dependent variables.

We suggest three reasons why neither of these studies (Alshdaifat et al., 2023; Bhagavathula et al., 2021; Gibbons et al., 2022) revealed an effect of lighting on measures of alertness. First, that the melanopic EDI level was still insufficient. Rather than using conditions suitable for application, it would be useful to use an extreme value, sufficient to reveal an effect, to demonstrate the experiment was sufficient. Second, in the study where participants were engaged in driving (Bhagavathula et al., 2021) the cognitive load of driving may have outweighed any variations in alertness due to changes in lighting: such results would therefore not represent pedestrians. Third, in those studies intended to represent pedestrians (Alshdaifat et al., 2023; Gibbons et al., 2022) the participants were either seated or walking slowly. When walking at a normal pace, the balance for walking demands greater cognitive attention (Al-Yahya et al., 2011; Patel et al., 2014) and this may affect the alertness measurements.

In this paper we report the findings from a further laboratory experiment, repeating the experiment of Alshdaifat et al. (Alshdaifat et al., 2023) but including a lighting condition providing a much higher level of melanopic EDI and walking at faster speed.

2 Method

The experiment was designed to investigate the alerting effect of light in a context simulating a typical evening, following a similar procedure to that of Alshdaifat et al. (2023). Forty healthy

test participants (median age 21 years, range 18 y to 29 y) attended the laboratory in pairs (Figure 1). A test session lasted for three hours. The first two hours were the adaptation period, for which they were seated under lighting representing a domestic interior (photopic illuminance of 25 lx at the eye, CCT = 2700 K, melanopic EDI = 10,7 lx). For the final hour they were exposed to one of the four test lighting conditions and both participants walked upon treadmills. The treadmills were set to a speed established before the adaptation period to be a moderate speed according to their heart rate (a mean speed across participants of 4,2 km·h⁻¹).

Figure 1 – Plan diagram of the laboratory

The four lighting conditions are shown in Table 1. The first lighting condition (L1) provided a vertical illuminance <0,5 lx at the eye and the same SPD as in the adaptation phase (melanopic EDI = <0,5 lx). Measurement of vertical illuminance on a small sample of minor roads revealed a range of <0,5 lx to 20 lx, which suggests that L1 resembled the lower end of the P-class. For L2 the illuminance at the eye was increased to 8 lx (melanopic EDI = 3,4 lx). L3 provided the same vertical illuminance at the eye as did L2, but with the CCT increased to 5800 K, increasing the melanopic EDI to 10,4 lx. L4 used the same SPD as L3 but with the vertical illuminance at the eye increased to 83 lx (melanopic EDI = 98,8 lx). These conditions extend beyond those were used in Bhagavathula et al. (2021), Gibbons et al. (2022) and Alshdaifat et al. (2023), having maximum melanopic EDIs of 0,8 lx, 5,7 lx and 10,7 lx respectively.

Table 1 – Illuminance and CCT for each of the test conditions

Exposure period	Lighting condition	Illuminance (lx)*	CCT (K)	Melanopic EDI (lx)
Adaptation	-	25	2700	10,7
Test	L1	<0,5	2700	<0,5
	L2	8	2700	3,4
	L3	8	5800	10,4
	L4	83	5800	98,8

* Vertical illuminances measured at eye level (1,5 m above the floor).

Participants were required to be (and confirmed by self-report) healthy (including no short and long-term medication, regular sleep, and being a non-smoker), having habitual bedtimes not later than midnight, not having been employed for night-time shift work in the past year, and not travelled over one or more time zones in the past three months. On the day of the experiment participants were asked to avoid consuming after midday any alcohol or caffeine and to refrain from napping.

Auditory reaction time (RT) and melatonin level were recorded at regular intervals throughout the adaptation and test phases. RT was measured using a psychomotor vigilance task (PVT). A 1000 Hz tone was played for 0,5s at random intervals ranging from 2s to 10s: test participants were instructed to press the response button as soon as they heard a stimulus. The loudness of the tone was determined separately for each participant according to their audibility threshold as measured during the pre-experiment period. Melatonin levels were determined from saliva samples as analysed by the Chorono@work laboratory (University of Groningen).

Both were measured at six intervals, 5min, 60min, 110min, 130min, 150min and 180min from the start of the experiment. The first three measurements were therefore in the adaptation phase and the latter three in the test lighting phase of the experiment. Saliva samples were collected at the interval point: the RT test was conducted for three minutes before and after each interval, with both sets combined for analysis.

3 Results

3.1 Reaction time

At a given measurement interval, for the two sets of RT trials, each test participant responded to approximately 60 acoustic stimuli. The data were cleaned by omitting assumed errors of omission (twice the median RT) and errors of assumed commission (RT < 100ms). Analysis of the responses in a given trial did not suggest they were drawn from a normal distribution and hence each trial was characterised by its median. This reduced the RT data to 40 responses (one per participant) at each of the six test intervals, and these data were not suggested to be normally distributed.

Figure 2 shows the median RT for the 40 participants at the six intervals where this was measured. Over the three-hour experiment, the median RT progressively decreased, suggested by the Friedman test to be a significant change across the intervals ($p < 0,0001$). A subsequent series of pairwise comparisons was conducted using post-hoc Wilcoxon tests. This indicated a longer RT at the first measurement interval (median RT = 379ms) than at the other test intervals ($p < 0,029$ in each case), and a shorter RT at the final test interval (median RT = 329ms) than the previous intervals ($p < 0,029$ in each case). Determinations of statistical significance were drawn with consideration to Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Figure 2 – Median reaction times at each test interval as measured using the acoustic PVT. Error bars show the Inter Quartile Range (IQR). During adaptation phase all participants were seated. * Test intervals within the initial two-hour adaptation period

For the adaptation phase, all participants were exposed to the same lighting condition and thus no differences were expected. Comparing the differences between groups therefore tests whether participants were fairly assigned to each group. The Kruskal-Wallis test did not suggest any differences to be significant ($p > 0,35$ in each case).

Figure 3 shows median RT for the adaptation phase (mean of the three intervals in the adaptation phase) and for each of the three intervals in the test phase. For three light conditions (L1, L2, and L3) the Friedman test did not suggest any differences to be significant ($p > 0,08$ in each case). In other words, the transition from the adaptation phase to the test phase did not change RT. For lighting condition L4, the condition of highest melanopic EDI, the Friedman test suggested a significant difference ($p = 0,001$): pairwise comparisons using the Wilcoxon test suggested that RT at the second (150min) and third (180min) intervals in the test phase were significantly shorter than the mean RT in the adaptation phase ($p < 0,01$).

Figure 3 – Median reaction times at the adaptation phase and at each test interval during the test phase according to the light condition during the test phase. Error bars show the Inter Quartile Range (IQR). The legend shows the melanopic EDI of each lighting condition. * Mean RT of the three intervals in the adaptation phase

3.2 Melatonin levels

Each participant provided saliva samples at six intervals from which were established melatonin levels. At any interval, the melatonin levels were not normally distributed. Figure 4 therefore shows the median melatonin level of the 40 participants at each interval. The melatonin levels progressively increased as the measurement interval approached habitual bedtimes. The Friedman test indicated a statistically significant difference in melatonin levels over time ($p < 0,0001$).

For the adaptation phase, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used to determine group differences at the same interval. There were no significant differences ($p > 0,51$ in each case), which suggests a fair distribution of participants across the four lighting conditions.

For the test phase, the-Kruskal Wallis test suggest a significant differences between the groups at the 150-minute interval (30 minutes after start of the test phase, $p = 0,045$) and the 180-minute interval (60 minutes after start of the test phase, $p = 0,004$), but not at the 130-minute interval (10 minutes after start of the test phase).

Figure 4 – Median melatonin levels derived from saliva samples collected at each test interval. Error bars show the Inter Quartile Range (IQR). * A test interval in the adaptation period

Figure 5 – Median melatonin levels at the adaptation phase and at each test interval during the test phase according to the light condition during the test phase. Error bars show the Inter Quartile Range (IQR). The legend shows the melanopic EDI of each lighting condition. * Mean of melatonin level of the three intervals in the adaptation phase

The effect of light condition on melatonin level was tested using the Friedman test, with the adaptation phase represented by the mean melatonin level across the three measurement intervals (Figure 5). For all four light conditions the Friedman test suggested significant changes across the measurement interval ($p < 0,03$ in each case). These were increases in melatonin levels under lighting conditions L1, L2, and L3, reaching their maximum levels at the end of the experiment. On the contrary, for light condition L4 (having the highest melanopic EDI), Figure 5 shows that the melatonin level peaks at the 130-minute interval and then decreases with ongoing exposure: pairwise comparisons using the Wilcoxon test suggested a significant decrease was in melatonin from the 150-minute to the 180-minute intervals ($p = 0,024$).

4 Conclusion

An experiment was conducted in which the effect of lighting on alertness was investigated in a context resembling pedestrian exposure in the evening. Two dependent variables were measured, RT to an acoustic stimulus and melatonin levels derived from saliva.

For melanopic EDI of up to 10 lx there were no statistically significant effects, confirming the previous findings of Bhagavathula et al., (2021); Gibbons et al., (2022) and Alshdaifat et al.,

(2023). However, increasing the melanopic EDI to 98,8 lx revealed a significant reduction in RT and a significant decrease in melatonin. However, this lighting condition is unlikely to be relevant for outdoor lighting, requiring either an illuminance of 83 lx with a CCT of 5800 K – or for the same melanopic EDI but a lower CCT, an illuminance of 230 lx at the eye for lighting of CCT 2700 K. In ongoing analyses, we are considering the effect of walking speed.

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